

Project no.:

763959

Project acronym:

MegaRoller

Project full title:

**Developing the PTO of the first MW-level
Oscillating Wave Surge Converter**

Collaborative project

H2020-LCE-2017-RES-RIA-TwoStage

Start date of project: 2018-05-01

Duration: 36 Months (3 years)

D5.3

Final LCA report of the MegaRoller device

Due Project Month: M33 (AMD-763959-9)

Due delivery date: 2020-01-31

Actual delivery date: 2020-01-29

Organisation name of lead beneficiary for this deliverable:

WavEC Offshore Renewables

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 Program (2014-2020)		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Deliverable number:	D5.4.2
Deliverable short title:	Final LCA Report
Deliverable title:	Final Life Cycle Assessment report of the MegaRoller device
Work package:	WP5 Validation & Impact Evaluation
Lead author:	WavEC / Apolonia, Maria
Author	WavEC / Apolonia, Maria

Revision Control			
Date	Revision	Author(s)	Comments
27.11.2020	1 st version	Maria Apolonia	Deliverable draft
01.12.2020	2 nd version	Risto Tiusanen, Minna Rääkkönen, Tero Välisalo (VTT)	Review
2.1.2021	3 rd version	Jussi Åkerberg (AWE)	Final review

Quality Assurance, status of deliverable		
Action	Performed by	Date
Verified (WP leader)	Risto Tiusanen (VTT)	01.12.2020
Verified (Sc Coordinator)	Jussi Åkerberg (AWE)	29.1.2021
Approved (Coordinator)	Ilpo Honkanen (Hydroll)	29.1.2021

Abstract

Goal - So far, very few studies have focused on the quantification of the environmental impacts of wave energy converters. The current study presents a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) of the MegaRoller wave energy converter, aiming to contribute to decision making regarding the least carbon and energy intensive design choices.

Methods - The LCA encompasses all life cycle stages from “cradle-to-grave” for the wave energy converter, including the panel, foundation, PTO and mooring system, considering its deployment in Peniche, Portugal. Background data was mainly sourced from the manufacturer whereas foreground data was sourced from the Ecoinvent database (v.3.4) and ReCiPe and CED impact assessment methods were applied.

Results and Discussion - The resulting impact assessment of the MegaRoller is aligned with all previous studies on MRE technologies in concluding the main environmental impacts are due to materials use and manufacture, while Assembly & Installation and O&M do not show significant impacts. The impact of manufacture is mainly due to high amounts of material used, particularly steel. Energy and carbon payback periods were both estimated to be around 28 months.

End-of-Life stage is currently excluded from operational boundaries of the majority of MRE developments and its inclusion in eco-design initiatives is challenged by uncertainties on a temporal, technological and business level such as uncertainties regarding recycling ratios. This report corroborated with previous studies by proving the importance of the End-of-Life scenario to the overall environmental performance and highlighted the need for further efforts to better understand how to model this stage.

The scenario analysis showed that there are alternative process and design choices that may increase the energy consumption and GHG emissions throughout the life cycle. While some scenarios showed a modest influence, others such as varying recycling rates and alternative material for stainless steel resulted in significant variations in the overall results.

The resulting GHG emissions and energy consumptions are generally comparable with earlier studies for wave and tidal technologies and are very low when compared with other power generating technologies. Opportunities to reduce the environmental impacts in the final design of the MegaRoller wave energy converter could potentially lie in reducing the quantity of steel by studying alternatives for its replacement.

Conclusions and Recommendations - The study confirms the effectiveness of LCA as a tool for assessing environmental impacts of marine renewable energy sources and comparing results with alternative energy sources and informing decisions for concept and product development.

Table of Contents

	Page
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	10
1.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).....	11
2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION	12
3 GOAL AND SCOPE	13
3.1 Goal.....	13
3.2 Scope.....	13
3.2.1 Functional Unit and Reference Flow.....	13
3.2.2 System Boundary	13
3.2.3 Tools and method of impact assessment	14
4 ANALYSIS OF THE MEGAROLLER LIFE CYCLE	16
4.1 Flowchart	16
4.2 Data Collection.....	17
4.2.1 Materials and manufacture	17
4.2.2 Assembly and Installation	20
4.2.3 Operation and Maintenance (O&M)	21
4.2.4 Decommissioning and Disposal	21
5 RESULTS	23
5.1 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)	23
5.2 Energy and carbon payback times	26
5.3 Alternative scenario analysis	27
6 DISCUSSION	29
6.1 Comparison with other studies of MREs	29
6.2 Comparison with other types of electricity generation.....	30
6.3 Potential for future improvement.....	31
7 CONCLUSIONS	33
8 REFERENCES	34

Table of Figures

	Page
Figure 1.1 - Life Cycle Assessment framework. Adapted from ISO 14040 (ISO 2006).	11
Figure 2.1 - Preliminary design of the MegaRoller device.	12
Figure 3.1 - System boundary for the LCA study.....	13

Figure 3.2 - Impact categories for characterization modelling at midpoint and endpoint levels (ReCiPe 2016).....	15
Figure 4.1 – Flowchart of the life cycle of MegaRoller.....	16
Figure 4.2 - Breakdown of materials (by mass).....	18
Figure 5.1 - Breakdown of impacts by life cycle stage for each impact category including CED (relative contribution).....	24
Figure 5.2 - Global Warming Potential.....	25
Figure 5.3 - Results of ReCiPe impact assessment method applied at endpoint level.....	26
Figure 5.4 - CED results.....	26
Figure 5.5 - Alternative scenarios (results are normalized compared to the baseline scenario).....	28
Figure 6.1 - Comparison of impacts of MegaRoller (OWSC) with other forms of energy production, presented relative to the highest score in each category.....	31

Table of Tables

	Page
Table 4.1 – Key parameters of MegaRoller.....	17
Table 4.2 – Material quantities for the LCA study not including pre-fabricated components.....	18
Table 4.3 – Device components and subcomponents – approximate weights.....	19
Table 4.4 – Transportation requirements during final device assembly by cargo ship to ENP.....	20
Table 4.5 – Sea vessel operations over device’s lifetime.....	21
Table 4.6 – Assumptions for EoL scenarios.....	22
Table 5.1 – Emissions of the Kyoto Protocol GHGs.....	23
Table 5.2 – Results of LCIA and CED calculation with acronyms.....	24
Table 5.3 – Parameters for scenario analysis.....	28
Table 6.1 – Carbon footprint and embodied energy estimates for a selection of MRE production studies.....	30

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

So far, very few studies have focused on the quantification of the environmental impacts of a wave energy converter. The current study presents a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) study of the MegaRoller wave energy converter, aiming to contribute to decision making regarding the least carbon and energy intensive design choices. The LCA encompasses all life cycle stages from “cradle-to-grave” for the wave energy converter, including the panel, foundation, PTO and mooring system, considering its deployment in Peniche, Portugal. Background data was mainly sourced from the manufacturer whereas foreground data was sourced from the Ecoinvent database (v.3.4) and ReCiPe and CED impact assessment methods were applied. The LCA application to the MegaRoller device resulted in a global warming potential (GWP) of 33.8 gCO₂ eq/kWh and Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) of 432 kJ/kWh. This LCA is aligned with all previous studies on MRE technologies in concluding the main environmental impacts are due to materials use and manufacture, while Assembly & Installation and O&M do not show significant impacts. The impact of manufacture is mainly due to high amounts of material used, particularly steel. Energy and carbon payback periods were both estimated to be around 28 months. End-of-Life stage is currently excluded from operational boundaries of the majority of MRE developments and its inclusion in eco-design initiatives is challenged by uncertainties on a temporal, technological and business level such as uncertainties regarding recycling ratios. This report corroborated with previous studies by proving the importance of the End-of-Life scenario to the overall environmental performance and highlighted the need for further efforts to better understand how to model this stage. The scenario analysis showed that there are alternative process and design choices that may improve the energy consumption and GHG emissions throughout the life cycle. While some scenarios showed a modest influence, others such as varying recycling rates and alternative material for stainless steel resulted in significant variations in the overall results. The resulting GHG emissions and energy consumptions are generally comparable with earlier studies for wave and tidal technologies and are very low when compared other power generating technologies. Opportunities to reduce the environmental impacts in the final design of the MegaRoller wave energy converter could potentially lie in reducing the quantity of steel by studying alternatives for its replacement. This study confirms the effectiveness of LCA as a tool for assessing environmental impacts of marine renewable energy sources and comparing results with alternative energy sources and informing decisions for concept and product development.

List of Acronyms

CCGT	Combined Cycle Gas Turbine
CED	Cumulative Energy Demand
CPT	Carbon Payback Time
ECU	Electrical Central Unit
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ENP	Estaleiros Navais de Peniche
EoL	End-of-Life
EPT	Energy Payback Time
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
HFC	Hydrofluorocarbons
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
HFO	Heavy Fuel Oil
ILCD	International Reference Life Cycle Data System
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCI	Life Cycle Inventory
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
MRE	Marine Renewable Energy
OWSC	Oscillating Wave Surge Converter
PFC	Perfluorocarbons
PTO	Power Take-Off
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RET	Renewable Energy Technology
WEC	Wave Energy Converter

1 INTRODUCTION

Wave power is seen as a promising opportunity for clean renewable energy supply. As a form of renewable energy, wave energy sources are low-impact and contribute to a more sustainable energy supply. However it is not environmentally friendly per se (Thomson et al. 2011) since energy is consumed and pollutants are emitted during the construction, operation and decommissioning of the energy converters. As the MRE sector develops, it is important to ensure that the technology proves to be a sustainable alternative (Collins 2014).

Holistic analysis with an energy trilemma perspective – economics, security of supply and environmental impacts – have been widely employed to assess potential benefits. However, to date, most studies provide only a qualitative analysis of the potential environmental impacts. There is little qualitative evidence to support decision makers. In particular, questions over whether these new technologies will deliver a net reduction in GHG emissions lead to the need for the use of a life cycle based approach, in order to assess all the emissions and energy consumption of a device (Uihlein 2016).

Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has been widely recognized as an efficient methodology to assess this subject by considering a technology's environmental performance over its life cycle. Since ocean energy is an emerging sector, only a few LCA have been performed on such technologies (Douglas et al. 2008; Parker et al. 2007; Uihlein 2016). In addition, most of these studies focus mainly on devices at an advanced stage of development (Magagna and Uihlein 2015) which poses an impediment to the use of the LCA as a support tool for decision making regarding the device design at early stages of the process. Good quality studies are lacking, especially for ocean thermal energy and salinity gradient technologies. Overall, the main impacts identified in ocean energy technologies are a result of raw material extraction, manufacturing processes, energy consumption and mooring systems (Paredes et al. 2019).

The development of the LCA on wave energy technologies is critical to overcome the current limitations and seize several advantages in the sector. Besides being useful for technology developers when deciding on the best design option for a certain device, this tool can also be of interest to potential investors, energy and government authorities who are considering the environmental implications of the product before investing or commissioning a project (Douglas et al. 2008). Finally, its quantitative nature fosters the comparison of environmental impacts associated with different energy generation systems (Elginos and Bas 2017).

This deliverable aim at adjusting the LCA methodology developed in the MegaRoller project to the final design of the MegaRoller device. The report presents a GHG emissions and cumulative energy demand audit of the final design of one 1MW MegaRoller device, encompassing all stages from cradle-to-grave. The document is structured as follows: after an introduction on LCA (Chapter 1), a description of the MegaRoller concept is presented (Chapter 2). Chapter 3 gives a comprehensive description of the goal and scope of the analysis including functional unit, system boundary and method of impact assessment applied. A full analysis of the MegaRoller life cycle is then presented (Chapter 4) by detailing data collection carried out in each stage from manufacture to the device's disposal. Main results of the Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA) are shown in Chapter 5 including calculations to achieve carbon and energy payback times as well as an analysis on a range of alternative scenarios regarding materials and operations. A comparison of these report results with other wave and tidal energy technologies as well as other means of electricity generation is undergone under Chapter 6, which also includes suggestions on potential future improvements for application of LCA in the MegaRoller. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Chapter 7.

1.1 Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

LCA is a valuable tool that allows the assessment of the cumulative environmental impacts of a system over space and time throughout its life cycle from cradle to grave i.e. from the extraction of raw materials until its disposal (EC-JRC 2010). Each stage of the life cycle (Figure 1.1) is analyzed in detail and data on the energy, materials, emissions and waste products associated are gathered. Justifiable assumptions are made when such information is not available.

The results are then described as a set of identifiable consequences or impact categories. This methodology complies with international standards ISO 14040:2006, which specifies the general framework, principles and requirements for conducting and reporting this type of assessment (ISO 2006). This standard describes the LCA as comprising four main stages: i) Goal and scope; ii) Inventory analysis; iii) Impact Assessment and iv) Interpretation. This analysis has the purpose of analyzing the components, materials or stages of the life cycle with the most significant environmental burdens. LCAs can help engineers and designers in the decision-making process regarding product design.

Figure 1.1 - Life Cycle Assessment framework. Adapted from ISO 14040 (ISO 2006).

According to (Curran 2015) there are four different types of LCA, depending on the goal of the analysis:

- Single system, results for internal use: assessment of a finished product to further search for opportunities to reduce its environmental impact;
- Single system, results for external use: disclosure of the environmental impacts of a product to the public;
- Comparative analysis, results for internal use: comparison of different designs or manufacture processes with the aim to assist on decision making;
- Comparative analysis, results for external use: results disclosure to the public on the environmental impact of a certain product of to advocate about possible legislations or bans affecting the product.

2 SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The MegaRoller concept is based on the existing design implemented and commercialized as WaveRoller, an oscillating wave surge converter (OWSC). This class of wave power technology uses bottom-hinged plates oscillating in pitch following the surge movement of the water particles in the nearshore zone (10 m - 25 m water depth) and is designed to absorb wave energy through horizontal motion of the prime mover. The wave surge moves the device's panel which is installed at approximately 8-20 meters of depth, approximately 400 m from shore. The device is anchored to the seabed and depending on tidal conditions it is mostly or fully submerged. Currently the anchors have an auxiliary function, hence they are only used in the installation phase.

The wave energy converted into motion by the panel is transmitted through a drivetrain to the power take-off (PTO) unit. The PTO is the core component that converts wave-induced oscillations from mechanical energy to electricity. It consists of two-cylinder units (one on each side of the panel) and one standardized power unit.

As the panel moves back-and-forth, the PTO's hydraulic pistons that have an interface with the panel via a drivetrain, pump hydraulic fluids inside a closed hydraulic circuit inside a hermetic structure. These cylinders are composed of single action pistons, one cylinder acting when the panel moves towards the coast, and another when the movement has the opposite direction. These high-pressure fluids are fed into a hydraulic motor that drives an electricity generator. The cylinders are sealed in a watertight compartment and are not exposed to the marine environment. The cylinders use the mechanical power applied to the pistons to compress the hydraulic fluid and store it in the accumulators. The accumulators help to attenuate the variation of the power produced, caused by the irregular profile of the incident waves. The energy stored in the accumulators is transferred through pressurized hydraulic flow to a hydraulic motor, followed by an electric generator that converts it into electrical energy. The electrical output is then connected to the electric grid via a subsea cable (AW Energy 2018).

The MegaRoller project aims at developing the PTO of the first MW-level OWSC generation, with a nominal capacity of 1 MW. The focus of the project is to design, build and validate a generic high performance, cost-efficient and reliable PTO that can be integrated into OWSC designs and therefore globally deployed in the energy sector. Figure 2.1 shows the main components of the MegaRoller device except for the mooring system.

Figure 2.1 - Preliminary design of the MegaRoller device.

3 GOAL AND SCOPE

3.1 Goal

The main purpose of this LCA study is to assess the environmental impacts of the final design of the MegaRoller device. The current study is built on the preliminary LCA report for early designs (D2.5) identifying the most important life cycle stages of the device regarding respective environmental impacts and a scenario analysis will support the identification of alternatives with the least impact considering all life cycle stages. The results will then be compared with other marine renewable technology and traditional means of electricity generation with the aim of identifying the benefits of using wave energy in comparison with other technologies. The LCA was conducted according to the International Reference Life Cycle Data (ILCD) System Handbook for LCA (EC-JRC 2010).

3.2 Scope

3.2.1 Functional Unit and Reference Flow

The functional unit (FU) used is 1 kWh of electricity delivered to the Portuguese electricity network by a 1 MW wave energy device with a reference flow of 1 MegaRoller device, as recommended by The International EPD System (2013). A single device is estimated to produce an average of 2.65 GWh/year over its 20-year lifespan.

3.2.2 System Boundary

The system boundary encompasses all life cycle stages from “cradle-to-grave” as recommended by Raventós et al. (2010), taking into consideration the production of each component parts, their assembly and transport to the installation site, deployment and O&M, as well as the process of decommissioning and disposal (Figure 3.1).

Figure 3.1 - System boundary for the LCA study.

Regarding the LCA physical boundaries, apart from the PTO itself, the analysis also covers the panel, foundation, and mooring system. The subsea cable connection to the grid as well as the substation and all parts of the onshore electricity network are outside the scope of this analysis. Since this is a descriptive study aiming at understanding the impact of a product and comparing it with other products with the same functional unit, the modelling principle for the Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) followed an attributional LCA approach (EC-JRC 2010).

The LCA will reflect a wave power device in design phase. Regarding the geographical boundaries, the device will be placed off the coast of Portugal, in Praia da Almagreira, Peniche. Manufacture is assumed to take place in Finland and Portugal, and the final assembly is assumed to take place in a fabrication yard in Estaleiros Navais de Peniche (ENP) followed by the device's installation. All data regarding extraction of raw materials, semi-finished products and components reflect the geographical region where the processes are assumed to take place. To allow comparison with other marine renewable technology and traditional means of electricity generation, carbon dioxide equivalent emissions per produced electricity ($\text{gCO}_2\text{eq/kWh}$) was the main unit defined for the study. This measure accounts for all six Kyoto GHG emissions: CO_2 , CH_4 , N_2O , HFC's, PFCs and SF_6 .

3.2.3 Tools and method of impact assessment

The SimaPro v8.5.2 was the LCA software used to model the system, with LCI data sourced from the Ecoinvent database (version 3.4). The impact assessment stage is achieved by translating the environmental loads from the inventory results into environmental impacts. The large number of inventory results is grouped in different impacts categories through the characterization of the results that cause a specific impact e.g. emissions of CO_2 , CH_4 and others contribute to the GHG effect with different weights defined according to their global warming potential. However different methods of impact assessment differ in the way each presents and weights the different impacts.

Midpoint and endpoint methods analyze different stages of the environmental impacts. Midpoint method is the most commonly adopted approach for LCA studies on ocean energy systems (Zhang et al. 2020). This LCIA was carried out with the ReCiPe 2016 Midpoint method (ReCiPe 2016), one of the most widely used midpoint impact assessment methods. It calculates 18 midpoint indicators which focus on single environmental problems. Endpoint indicators show the environmental impact on three higher aggregation levels. Converting midpoints to endpoints increases uncertainty in the results since some level of weighting is required, which leads to invalid results for comparison purposes. However, midpoint impact potentials are considered as more abstract and difficult to interpret. CO_2 emissions and embodied energy are two examples as they do not provide information about the damaging effects of increased levels of GHGs or energy consumption. Furthermore, this aggregation simplifies the interpretation of the LCIA results, and the entire impact pathway is accounted for. Hence, the assessment at an endpoint level was also included (Figure 3.2). Although all impact categories were analyzed, climate change was the main target since the results are easier to communicate due to the current political focus on the field and because it was proved adequate for the identification overall hotspots (Bonou et al. 2016). In addition, an energy input assessment was carried out using Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) to calculate the total direct and indirect amount of energy consumed throughout the life cycle (Frischknecht and Jungbluth 2007).

Figure 3.2 - Impact categories for characterization modelling at midpoint and endpoint levels (ReCiPe 2016).

4 ANALYSIS OF THE MEGAROLLER LIFE CYCLE

4.1 Flowchart

All processes from raw material extraction to disposal are covered by the LCA, as shown in the flowchart below (Figure 4.1). Each stage of the life cycle of the MegaRoller is explained in more detail in this chapter. The manufacture of prefabricated components is not considered but the materials they are made of are, hence the red color given to this box.

Figure 4.1 – Flowchart of the life cycle of MegaRoller.

4.2 Data Collection

Foreground or primary data were collected from the project design team, material experts and engineers. All background or secondary data were ultimately derived from the Ecoinvent database (v.3.4). Assumptions and approximations for non-available data are explained in this section. Since the Ecoinvent database does not contain all inventory information, some manufacture processes were modeled according to the energy consumed using data sourced elsewhere and new materials were created based on previous studies.

Most data in this database reflect the average European conditions. One exception is electricity production, for which data is provided by country. This means that, for manufacturing processes assumed to take place e.g. in Finland (country code FI), the electricity mix used was changed to Finnish electricity mix. For processes taking place in an unknown (European or global) location, the average European (code RER) or global (code GLO) electricity mix was used.

A wave energy device consists of many components and sub-components of different nature and with several mechanical and electrical parts. Therefore, it is difficult to gather from suppliers' information on all the parts. This analysis focused therefore on the most important components. Given the expected small contribution of some electronic and electrical systems to the overall embodied carbon and considering their complexity, it was more appropriate to simplify this stage to avoid time consumption. Thus, a cut-off criterion of 1% was applied throughout the life cycle to exclude minor impacts and help set boundaries for the total system inventory (Dahlsten 2009). As wave energy devices only produce electricity and e.g. no heat, there is no need to allocate between more products, which simplifies the inventory. A set of key parameters is clearly summarized in **Error! Reference source not found.** Table 4.1 – Key parameters of MegaRoller. Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 – Key parameters of MegaRoller.

Parameter	Value
Number of WECs	1
Location	Peniche, Portugal
WEC rated power/nominal capacity?	1000 kW
WEC average power	320 kW
PTO efficiency	88%
Power efficiency (wave to wire)	25%
Operation lifetime	20 years
Annual Energy Production (per device)	2.1-3.2 GWh
Distance from shore	400 m

4.2.1 Materials and manufacture

The life cycle begins with the raw material extraction and processing followed by the manufacture phase which comprises the moulding and shaping of the materials to form the device sub-components. MegaRoller is largely constructed from steel and cement. Steel is cut and welded to shape before being

painted with corrosion-resistant paint. A mass-based analysis was carried out for the device with a breakdown of the materials used in

Table 4.2 and **Error! Reference source not found.** with data provided by the manufacturer. Over 70% of the total mass of the MegaRoller is concrete. The manufacture of each main component is described in this section. Table 4.3 shows the components and subcomponents considered in this analysis.

Stock Material	Quantity (ton)
Concrete	2828
Low-alloyed steel	423
Reinforcing steel	398
Stock Material	Quantity (ton)
Concrete	2828
Cast iron	148
Low-alloyed steel	423
Iron scrap	34
Reinforcing steel	398
Total	3987
Stainless steel	156
Cast iron	148
Iron scrap	34
Total	3987

Table 4.2 – Material quantities for the LCA study not including pre-fabricated components.

Figure 4.2 - Breakdown of materials (by mass).

4.2.1.1 Foundation

The foundation supports the panel, is of a gravitational type and made of reinforced concrete. AWE gave an approximate concrete volume of 1173.9 m³, which was converted in around 2817 ton assuming a weight of approximately 2400 kg per m³ of concrete (NRMCA 2008). The structure is manufactured in ENP, through processes of moulding, steel reinforcing, placing, and curing of concrete. Since Ecoinvent doesn't include processes of manufacture deemed appropriate, the study considered only an estimate of the energy consumption for concrete moulding (Duque Ciceri et al. 2010).

4.2.1.2 Panel

It is estimated by the manufacturer that the panel will be a 26x10 m structure and 4.7 m thick at its thickest point just below the sea surface at mean tidal level. It will have an approximate mass of 358 ton consisting of a welded steel structure and it is assumed to be manufactured in Finland. Panel castings are assumed to be manufactured in Turkey. Final subassembly, including assembly with panel bearings, is assumed to take place in ENP.

The steel plates go through processes of welding, machining, and hot rolling until desired shape after which the panel is assumed to be painted with a corrosion-resistant paint. The process of painting was created based on assumptions made by R. Camilla Thomson, Chick, and Harrison (2019). The paint was assumed to cover an area of 4493m².

The energy consumption for the machining processes was based on Ashby (2013) assuming an average consumption of 8 MJ/kg of processed steel and 10 MJ/kg for casting iron. Calculations for the welding process were undergone assuming the need of 4.35 kg of weld steel per meter (Lincoln Electric 2019).

4.2.1.3 Power take-off (PTO)

The PTO is structured in two main systems: hydraulic system and electrical system. All the hydraulic components of the PTO are contained in the two side units. Hydraulic cylinders, accumulators, motors and generators are all stored in each side unit, while the electrical central unit (ECU) contains only electrical components: transformer and frequency converter. The central unit is connected to the side units (hulls) via electric cables. The PTO's subcomponents considered in the analysis are shown in Table 4.3.

Since the hydraulic components of the ECU are all contained in one hull, each entire hydraulic module can be manufactured, assembled, tested, and delivered ready for deployment. This limits the potential environmental impact by decreasing the amount of assembly that needs to occur on the barge. Excepting the component housing, the electrical system components are prefabricated and therefore their manufacture processes were excluded from the analysis.

The hydraulic system consists of two main assemblies, the power unit and the drivetrain. The purpose of the drivetrain module is to produce counter moment for the panel of WaveRoller. It also transforms mechanical movement into hydraulic energy. Main components of the drivetrain unit are the hydraulic cylinders and the mechanism. The power unit module transforms hydraulic energy into electrical energy. It houses main hydraulic accumulator racks (350 in total, weighting approximately 97 kg each) and hydraulic motor-electric generator packages. Except for the components housing and the hydraulic cylinders, which go through manufacture processes of welding, machining, casting and hot rolling, the hydraulic system components are prefabricated and therefore their manufacture processes were excluded from the analysis. The hydraulic accumulators' detailed were supplied by Hydroll, the manufacturer. The components' housing is painted with the same type of paint as the panel but, since no data was given for the dimensions, the process of painting was excluded from the analysis.

4.2.1.4 Mooring system

Since no data was provided by the manufacturer, assumptions were made for the mooring system based on previous studies. The mooring system is assumed to comprise 4 sets of chromium steel chains connected to a concrete anchor. The set will attach to the device to ensure that it remains where it will be installed, given the highly dynamic and energetic characteristics of this coastal area. Since two anchors are already on site, the analysis only considers the manufacture of 4 chains and 2 anchors. Each chain is assumed to have 130 m of length and weight approximately 28.5 tons (Zepeda 2017). Welding (for chains) and heavy machining (for anchors) were the processes considered. Chains are assumed to be manufactured through arc welding (Lincoln Electric 2019), whose heating source is the use of an electric arc that is placed between the tip of a covered electrode and the desired surface of the metal being weld (Kou 1987).

Table 4.3 – Device components and subcomponents – approximate weights.

Component	Total Weight	Subcomponent	Material (and weight)
PTO	1.5 ton	Transformer	857 kg steel 643 kg other materials
	40.0 ton	Hydraulic pipes and tubes	40.0-ton chromium steel
	3.2 ton	4 Generators	≈3.2-ton steel
	2.4 ton	4 Hydraulic Motors	2.4-ton chromium steel
	34.0 ton	350 Piston accumulators	≈34.0-ton iron scrap
	212.0 ton	2 Components housing	130.0-ton steel 80.0 ton cast iron 2.0-ton paint

Panel	357.0 ton	Main structure	221.0-ton steel 68.0 ton cast iron
		2 Panel bearings	68.0-ton steel
Foundation	3215.1 ton	-	2817.3-ton concrete
		-	397.8 ton reinforcing steel
Mooring System	124.3 ton	2 anchors	10.4-ton concrete
		4 chains	113.9-ton chromium steel

4.2.2 Assembly and Installation

The assembly involves the transport of each subcomponent to the fabrication yard for final device assembly before the installation. The energy used for transportation of the components is done by multiplying the distance (km) by the weight (kg), as shown in Table 4.4 – foundation was not included since it is manufactured in the harbor. The ‘tkm’ is the functional unit for transport, and represents the transport of 1000 kg goods over 1 km. Since no data was provided for the exact location of manufacture, estimates for distances were made based on the location between ENP and the main port in each case. The PTO’s subassembly is assumed to take place in Finland with the final device assembly take place in ENP (Portugal). Very generic assumptions regarding transport throughout the analysis are justified by the fact that results show the environmental impacts of transport are not significant compared with other life cycle stages.

Table 4.4 – Transportation requirements during final device assembly by cargo ship to ENP.

Component	Weight (ton)	Manufacturing/ Source location	Distance to ENP (km)	Payload Distance (tkm)
Mooring system	124.3	China	19820	24632230
Panel	289	Finland	3635.5	105066
Panel bearings	68	UK	1354	92072
PTO	293.2	Finland	3635.5	1065786

A 60-tonne overhead crane and fork-lift trucks are needed for final assembly. Since no data from the manufacturer was available and the impacts of final assembly are expected to be relatively small, a rough estimation taken from Thomson (2014) was used. A 60-tonne overhead crane was assumed to work for 4.7 hours consuming 18 kWh from the Portuguese grid. A typical fork-lift truck is estimated to consume 2.55 L/hr (Caterpillar 2019). Ecoinvent data for the combustion of diesel in equipment is given per unit of energy consumed, so the density of diesel was assumed to be 0.8325 kg/L and the specific energy to be 43 MJ/kg to convert this volumetric data to a fuel consumption of 91.3 MJ/hr (EC 2009).

After final assembly, specialist sea vessels are required to install moorings, prepare the seabed, tow and install the device.

The installation site must be prepared to seat the device on the bottom using a technique called ‘jetting’ which consists in using pressurized water jets to level the bottom horizontally. This process was excluded from the analysis. In addition to the two concrete anchors already installed in the installation site, two other cemented anchors will be transported by a freight boat and attached to the MegaRoller device

through cables (chains). The anchors will be submerged prior to submerging the device and pulled by a tugboat to be buried in the bottom.

This type of foundation can be installed in any homogeneous seabed which is typically the case for sandy seabed. As the gravity foundation floats when filled with air, the MegaRoller can be towed from ENP to the site where it is connected to auxiliary anchors to keep it in the right location. This operation will be done by towing boats aided by an assistance vessel. The foundation is then filled with water and the system is slowly submerged down to the seabed. This process is modeled as fuel consumed as there is no complete life cycle data for towing boats available.

The device is towed for about 16 km from the harbor to the installation site. The overall estimated duration of the installation stage is 12 hours. According to the manufacturer data, two tugboats will be required to tow the device for 4 hours and to stand-by during deployment for another 8 hours which accounts for a total diesel consumption of 8800 liters. Resource use and emissions were approximated by scaling Ecoinvent data for a freight ship to match fuel consumption of each type of vessel, as suggest by Thomson, Chick, and Harrison (2019). Data for density of Heavy Fuel Oil (HFO) was taken from (Vermiere 2012).

4.2.3 Operation and Maintenance (O&M)

During operation, the device is remotely monitored which is likely to have relatively low environmental impacts therefore none are considered during the device operational phase.

Maintenance activities will be essentially onsite by activating the buoyancy system, requiring an inspection vessel for small interventions (Table 4.5). Since this information wasn't provided by the manufacturer, the study assumed 1,3 days of sea vessel operations per year and a fuel consumption of 500 L/day (Thomson et al. 2019).

According to previous studies on the WaveRoller, major maintenance is assumed to be undergone every 5 years and these are expected to take place in the ENP. The system is lifted back to the surface by pumping air into the chambers. Then the MegaRoller is towed to the harbor. This results in an estimation of 3 days of operations, including tow to shore and redeployment, over the device's lifetime. The barge foundation allows easy recovery of the device, which reduces service and maintenance costs. When the mooring system needs maintenance, the installation process is performed in reverse. Following Parker et al. (2007) and Thomson et al. (2011) this analysis considers that no major part has to be replaced during the 20-year lifetime which may underestimate impacts from this stage.

Table 4.5 – Sea vessel operations over device's lifetime.

Sea vessel	Fuel Consumption (L/day)	Total days of operation
Installation		
Tugboat	8800	1
Maintenance		
Tugboat	1490	3
Inspection vessel	500	26
Decommissioning		
Tugboat	8800	1

4.2.4 Decommissioning and Disposal

This phase represents an important part of the LCA that could contribute to an improvement in the overall environmental impact by giving credits to the emissions released in the other stages. The recycled material substitutes virgin material and hence avoids environmental impacts from the production of new materials. It also includes the transport to the disposal site or recycling plant. At this stage, it is worth mentioning that attention should be paid in order not to double-count impacts on both waste treatment and impacts associated with primary material extraction (Thomson 2014).

Decommissioning the MegaRoller will require the use of sea vessels to unlatch the technology, tow the Wave Energy Converter (WEC) to shore and recover some of the mooring system. Type of sea vessels and fuel consumption at this stage were assumed to be the same as in during the installation of the device as shown in Table 4.5. The MegaRoller is re-floated to the surface, the electrical cable is disconnected, and chains of the additional anchors are loosened. The device is then towed to the harbor of Peniche. The mooring system is lifted to the surface using hoisting booms and is towed back to the harbor.

The disposal scenario of the MegaRoller device baseline design assumed no environmental impacts from disassembly processes. Waste is expected to follow two different End-of-Life (EoL) routes based on literature – recycling and landfilling (Table 4.6). At the EoL of the device, two anchors and two chains will be left on the sea bottom. Following similar assumptions made in other studies for the technology, metal components are assumed to be transported to a recycling center and the concrete blocks re crushed and re-used. Since there is still little knowledge on end of life for wave energy devices, this can be considered a rough estimate. Following a similar methodology adopted in a previous study (Bonou et al. 2016), recycling leads to materials recovery, thus avoiding respective production from virgin sources. Transport to final disposal site was considered negligible compared to other life cycle stages and thus is excluded from the analysis. An examination of the sensitivity of the chosen recycling scenario is described in detail in Section 5.3. Stainless steel hardly ever becomes waste after its EoL since it contains other valuable raw materials such as chromium and nickel which makes recycling economically viable.

Table 4.6 – Assumptions for EoL scenarios.

Material	Type of disposal and ratios
Low alloyed and Stainless Steel	Recycle 85%% Waste treatment 15%
Concrete	Recycle 85%, Waste treatment 15%
Cast Iron	Recycle 70%, Waste treatment 30%

5 RESULTS

5.1 Life Cycle Impact Assessment (LCIA)

The LCI produced a list of around 1500 substances consumed or emitted throughout the life cycle. Table 5.1 shows the total life cycle emissions of the six Kyoto GHG for the MegaRoller. Although further calculations are required, it is already visible that CO₂ emissions are significant which mostly arise during steel manufacture.

Table 5.1 – Emissions of the Kyoto Protocol GHGs.

Gas		Emissions (g/kWh)	GWP (g CO ₂ eq/kWh)
Carbon Dioxide	CO ₂	38.4	38.40
Methane	CH ₄	0.132	4.76
Nitrous Oxide	N ₂ O	0.00148	0.44
Sulphur Hexafluoride	SF ₆	2.48E-06	0.06
Hydrofluorocarbons	HFC	1.1E-05	0.03
Perfluorocarbons	PFC	1.70E-06	0.01

The ReCiPe impact assessment method was applied to characterize the results of the LCI and the environmental impacts summarized in Table 5.2. A cut-off criterion of 1% was applied in order to visualize the most relevant contributors. Since ocean energy is being broadly considered as a technology that will contribute to a low-carbon energy system, special attention was given to the LCA results on the global warming potential (GWP). Nevertheless, an overview of all 18 impacts from both ReCiPe and CED impact assessment methods is summarized in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2 – Results of LCIA and CED calculation with acronyms.

Impact Category		
Global Warming Potential (GWP)	33.8	g CO₂ eq/kWh
Stratospheric ozone depletion (SOD)	11.5	µg CFC-11/kWh
Ionizing radiation (IR)	1.6	Bq Co-60 eq/kWh
Ozone formation, Human health (OF Hum)	115.0	mg NOx eq/kWh
Fine particulate matter formation (FPMF)	6.4	mg PM2.5 eq/kWh
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems (OF Eco)	118.0	mg NOx eq/kWh
Terrestrial acidification (TA)	-90.7	mg SO ₂ eq/kWh
Freshwater eutrophication (F Eut)	4.0	mg P eq/kWh
Marine Eutrophication (M Eut)	1.1	mg N eq/kWh
Terrestrial ecotoxicity (T Etox)	236.0	g 1,4-DCB /kWh
Freshwater ecotoxicity (F Etox)	2.2	g 1,4-DCB /kWh
Marine ecotoxicity (M Etox)	2.8	g 1,4-DCB /kWh
Human carcinogenic toxicity (HT car)	-6.6	g 1,4-DCB /kWh
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity (HT noncar)	22.3	g 1,4-DCB /kWh
Land use (LU)	10.9	cm ² a crop eq/kWh
Mineral resource scarcity (MRS)	1.1	g CU eq/kWh
Fossil resource scarcity (FRS)	7.0	g oil eq/kWh
Water Consumption (WC)	310	cm ³ /kWh
Cumulative Energy Demand (CED)	432.0	kJ/kWh

Figure 5.1 - Breakdown of impacts by life cycle stage for each impact category including CED (relative contribution).

The **global warming potential (GWP)** was found to be **33.8 g CO₂ eq/kWh** and the **CED** to be **432 kJ/kWh**. These values rise to 75.1 g CO₂ eq/kWh and 1010 kJ/kWh if the disposal scenario is excluded, highlighting the crucial role this uncertain stage plays in the overall life cycle. Figure 5.1 illustrates the contribution of the life cycle stages to each impact category. The level of contribution depends on the impact category that is being valued but some trends can be observed. The manufacture of each individual subcomponent is displayed separately. Transport of the subcomponents to the harbour for final assembly as well as the transport of the device of the installation site are included in the Assembly & Installation. For almost all impact categories, manufacture contributes the most environmental impacts, particularly the foundation. Freshwater and marine eutrophication and mineral resource scarcity impacts are linked mainly to the manufacture of steel. Energy consumption (due to electricity generation) has effects on categories such as human toxicity and global warming potential.

The results for the impact category GWP are shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** in g CO₂ eq/kWh. Impacts related to Assembly & Installation and O&M (1.88% and 1.89%, respectively) have a small impact in the overall results whereas the manufacture stage has the biggest impact of all life cycle stages. Transport contributes 5,3% to the overall GWP results. The manufacture of the foundation accounts for 42% (approx. 32 g CO₂ eq/kWh) of the impacts during this stage (before applying credits for recycling). These impacts are largely due to the fact that cement production is very energy-intensive, and thus contributes substantial GHG emissions. The manufacture of the PTO, mooring system, and panel account for 18,6%, 14,8% and 21,5%, respectively.

Figure 5.2 - Global Warming Potential.

The results of the impact assessment at end-point level are shown in Figure 5.3, where emissions are related to their damages to the three areas of protection: ecosystems quality, human health and natural resources. It can be seen that the contribution of each life cycle stage is fairly even across the three areas.

Figure 5.3 - Results of ReCiPe impact assessment method applied at endpoint level.

The annual energy production of the MegaRoller is estimated to be between 2.1 and 3.2 GWh, which results in an energy intensity of 432 kJ/kWh, as previously illustrated (Table 5.2). The CED is calculated for five classes of primary energy carriers: fossil, nuclear, hydro, biomass, and others (wind, solar and geothermal). Differences for different types of cumulative energy demands are mainly due to the consideration of location-specific electricity mixes. The preponderance of non-renewables energies, especially energy from fossil fuels, is clearly observable (Figure 5.4), where for each kWh of electricity, 320 kJ of fossil energy is used i.e., 74% of the total energy demand comes from fossil fuels.

Figure 5.4 - CED results.

5.2 Energy and carbon payback times

Energy and Carbon payback time (EPT and CPT, respectively) are important indicators for renewable resources. CPT measures the period (months) required for the MegaRoller to offset the carbon emissions generated throughout the device’s life cycle process and is calculated according to Equation (1). The energy payback time (EPT) represents the amount of time that the system needs to run in order to produce the

amount of energy equivalent to the primary energy consumed throughout its life time and is calculated according to Equation (2).

$$CO_2eq \text{ payback } (CPT) = \frac{\text{Total } CO_2eq \text{ emissions throughout life cycle } (gCO_2eq)}{\text{Annual } CO_2eq \text{ avoided}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Energy payback time } (EPT) = \frac{\text{Life Cycle Embodied Energy}}{\text{Energy produced } (EP)_{year}} \quad (2)$$

The carbon avoided by the device will depend on what generation is displaced and is time and location dependent. However, it is accepted practice to assume that the electricity offset by the device will be the average of the Portuguese grid, with a CO₂ intensity of 0.295 kg CO₂/kWh (Moro and Lonza 2017). The GWP and CED were found in section 5 to be 33.8 g CO₂ eq/kWh and 432 kJ/kWh, respectively. These values correspond to a CPT of 2.3 years and an EPT of 2.4 years.

5.3 Alternative scenario analysis

There are several potential sources of uncertainty in this study arising from the early stage of wave energy developments in general and from non-availability of data for MegaRoller in particular. A range of scenarios was drawn (Table 5.3) to assess that uncertainty and, consequently, to model potential improvements in the life cycle environmental impact. Results presented in this section are indicative and results interpretation need further study regarding the sensitivity of each parameter variation. Although concrete makes about 88% of the overall foundation's weight, reinforcing steel is responsible for 54.3% of the GWP in the manufacture of the foundation. As such, a scenario was drawn for the substitution of steel reinforced concrete foundation by a glass fibre reinforced concrete foundation (Figure 5.5). Considering this substitution happens on a percentage of 0.5% of the concrete weight (Preetha et al. 2014), a potential reduction of 24% in GHG emissions can be observed. Such a significant reduction should be taken into account when studying this and other alternative materials for this component. Considering the large contribution that stainless steel makes to environmental impacts, the whole amount of this material needed for the MegaRoller manufacture was substituted by low alloyed steel, resulting in a decrease of 28% in the overall carbon intensity. By assuming the manufacture of the whole device near the installation site, a potential reduction of 5% in carbon intensity can be observed, which might indicate that transport of components is not significant in the overall global warming potential impacts. An alternative scenario was drawn for waste treatment, by varying the recycling ratio for steel. A decrease of 35% in the recycling ratio for steel resulted in an increase in almost 24% in the carbon emissions. This variation shows the importance of this parameter and that special attention should be given for the EoL of the MegaRoller device. Further attention should also be given to the recycling ratio of concrete. Increasing the device's lifetime means increasing the average production of the device over its lifetime from 53 GWh to 79.5 GWh. These alternative results in a carbon intensity of 22.4 g CO₂ eq/kWh, which means a decrease of 33% compared to the baseline scenario.

Table 5.3 – Parameters for scenario analysis.

Assumptions	Scenario	
	Baseline Scenario	Alternative Scenarios
Alternative material choice for foundation reinforcement	Steel reinforcement	Glass fibre reinforcement
Alternative material for stainless steel	Stainless steel	Low alloyed steel
Manufacture Locations	UK, Finland, Turkey, Italy	Portugal (close to installation site)
Waste Scenario for Steel	Recycling rate 85%	Recycling rate 50 %
Higher lifetime reflecting an increased durability	20 years	30 years

MegaRoller demands a high input of materials per installed capacity (3987 kg/kW) when compared with other renewable energy technologies, e.g. 330 to 360 kg/kW for photovoltaic systems (Krauter 2006) and 340 to 770 kg/kW for wind turbines (Guezuraga et al. 2012). Therefore, and since steel is one of the largest contributors to the overall GWP impacts, another scenario considered was the use of lightweight materials such as the use of aluminum. This would involve greater specific environmental impacts per kg of material but also a possible reduction in impacts due to the lower material of material used. However, there was a lot of uncertainty around this scenario e.g. the extent of which the structural weight could be reduced, so the results weren't considered to be robust enough; this might be studied in future technologies.

Figure 5.5 - Alternative scenarios (results are normalized compared to the baseline scenario).

6 DISCUSSION

As previously stated, very few LCA have been carried out in the context of marine renewable energies which makes it difficult to draw conclusions about wave and tidal energy from the existing literature, as no clear consensus or trend in the results can be observed. In addition, comparison between LCAs is only truly valid if studies are based on the same characterization factors and methodology. Nonetheless, a comparison of the results with current literature for other wave or ocean energy and other means of energy production was carried out.

6.1 Comparison with other studies of MREs

The study results' are consistent with Uihlein's results on GWP for a similar device (2016) as part of a very complete study on LCA of ocean energy technologies which analyses the GWP for 15 tidal and wave technologies. It concludes that total GHG emissions range from 15 g CO₂ eq/kWh for enclosed-tip devices to 105 g CO₂ eq/kWh for point absorber and rotating mass devices, with an average of 53±29 g CO₂ eq/kWh for all technologies. However, the PTO was the subcomponent that accounted for more GHG emissions for the OWSC device assessed in this study, whereas the foundation is the biggest contributor in the case of MegaRoller during manufacture. Like MegaRoller though, the proportions of O&M and Assembly & Installation are almost negligible for all device types.

Table 6.1 shows the studies used to benchmark MegaRoller results with other ocean energy systems. Dahlsten (2009) conducted LCA of a WEC and concluded that most of the impacts are related to the material used besides installation, maintenance and decommissioning cannot be disregarded. Offshore wind converters are the less carbon intensive technologies (also compared with other means of electricity generation in Section 6.2). Thomson, Chick, and Harrison (2019) revealed that Pelamis WEC emits 35 gCO₂ eq/kWh and has a CED of 493 kJ/kWh as results of an LCA study, the closest values from MegaRoller results among the reviewed literature. Walker and Howell (2011) used LCA to assess environmental burdens of Oyster wave energy converter and SeaGen tidal turbine comparatively. Despite being both oscillating body systems with hydraulic PTOs and largely made of steel, differences in results between Pelamis and Oyster might be due to differences in technology but could also be due to variations in analysis methodology and assumptions. The carbon footprint of Wave Dragon, a floating overtopping device is comparatively lower which might be because of being predominantly made of concrete. Douglas, Harrison, and Chick (2008) assessed carbon and energy intensity of SeaGen, a marine current turbine, having identified manufacture as the main contributor to the results and suggested a couple of improvements through the use of alternative materials with greater recycling potential. Dalton, Madden, and Clare Daly (2014) identified the cradle to gate phase as the most intensive phase for all parameters.

Table 6.1 – Carbon footprint and embodied energy estimates for a selection of MRE production studies.

Device	Carbon intensity (g CO ₂ eq/kWh)	Energy intensity (kJ/kWh)	Reference
Wave energy converters			
MegaRoller	33.8	432	
Oyster	25	236	(Walker and Howell 2011)
Pelamis	35	493	(Thomson et al. 2019)
Wave Dragon	13	-	(Hans Chr., Sørensen Stefan et al. 2007)
Wavestar	47	536	(Dalton et al. 2014)
Point absorber	39-126	-	(Dahlsten 2009)
BRD WEC	89	387	(Zhai et al. 2018)
OBREC WEC	37	-	(Patrizi et al. 2019)
Tidal energy converters			
SeaGen	15	214	(Douglas et al. 2008)
Deepgen	10.7	140	(Elmehag and Torosian 2013)
Openhydro	19.6	-	(Walker et al. 2015)
Scotrenewables	23.8	-	(Walker et al. 2015)
Tidal turbines	8.6	149	(Rule et al. 2009)
Offshore wind converters			
Offshore wind turbine	11	-	(Bonou et al. 2016)

6.2 Comparison with other types of electricity generation

The MegaRoller aims to be a low-carbon alternative to conventional power generation, but it is expected that it will have lower environmental impacts across all categories, in particular eutrophication, depletion of fossil fuels, toxic effects on humans and ecosystems and ozone formation. Figure 6.1 summarizes the environmental impacts caused by the production of 1 kWh of electricity of a range of other means of electricity generation from Ecoinvent database. Values are shown as relative to the highest score in each impact category. MegaRoller has significantly lower impacts than coal and gas-fired generation (combined cycle gas turbine or CCGT) in GWP, ozone formation and depletion, fossil resource scarcity and CED. However, nuclear and CCGT have a better performance in a range of other categories such as Land use or Ecotoxicity. MegaRoller was found to have the highest impacts in mineral resource scarcity – this category uses quantity of minerals and fossil fuels used and converts this LCA data to a ratio of quantity of resource used versus quantity of resource left in the reserve. Regarding GWP, onshore and offshore wind and nuclear perform better than MegaRoller. This comparison shows the importance of assessing more than the GWP and energy consumption for renewable technologies.

It can also be seen that other renewable technologies such as onshore and offshore wind perform better than MegaRoller in terms of GHG emissions. Offshore wind was in fact found to be the technology with the lowest GHG emissions for electricity and heat generation from renewable energy technologies (RETs) according to Yaw Amponsah et al. (2014), with a carbon intensity of 5.3–13 g CO₂ eq/kWh. Some studies come to energy and carbon intensity levels that are in range with those of MegaRoller, namely 35 to 50 g

CO₂ eq/kWh for wind and solar PV respectively (Nugent and Sovacool 2014), 20-80 g CO₂ eq/kWh for concentrated solar power (Burkhardt et al. 2012) and 40-80 g CO₂ eq/kWh for geothermal (Frick et al. 2010). However, it is very important to remember that these are much more established technologies than MRE. As demonstrated in Section 5.1, almost all the energy consumed throughout the device’s life cycle derives from fossil fuels which is a direct effect of the current fossil-based global economy. This will potentially change as global infrastructure and technology evolves.

Figure 6.1 - Comparison of impacts of MegaRoller (OWSC) with other forms of energy production, presented relative to the highest score in each category.

6.3 Potential for future improvement

This report identified the materials, processes and life cycle stages that contribute to global warming and energy consumption. It is expected that this information is used by manufacturers choosing the best design and improving the operations throughout the WEC’s life cycle. As an example, an opportunity to reduce environmental impacts could lie with the substitution of reinforcing steel in the manufacture of the foundation (responsible for 42% of the overall GHG emissions) by another material such as glass fiber. The improvement of the MegaRoller mooring system should also be an area of further research, which is currently being undertaken by AW Energy through replacing stainless-steel chains by steel wire. In this scenario, the mooring system is merely used to keep the assembly steady during submersions.

There are several potential sources of uncertainty in this study arising from the early stage of wave energy developments in general and from non-availability of data for MegaRoller in particular. The scenario

analysis intended to assess some of that uncertainty however this analysis should be further deepened in the final LCA through a full sensitivity analysis.

In order to understand the realistic impacts of wave energy devices at commercial scale, this study should also be carried out considering, not one MegaRoller device but an array of devices, which would certainly reduce environmental impacts per kWh of electricity produced since sharing some components (e.g. foundation systems) will certainly reduce the material intensity.

7 CONCLUSIONS

This LCA was intended to choose the least carbon intensive design option for the WEC and opting for the most efficient processes throughout the device's life cycle. The resulting carbon intensity of 33.8 gCO₂ eq/kWh and energy intensity of 432 kJ/kWh are generally comparable with earlier studies for wave and tidal technologies and are very low when compared to other power generating technologies. This LCA is aligned with all previous studies on MRE technologies in concluding the main environmental impacts are due to materials use and manufacture, while Assembly & Installation and O&M do not show significant impacts. High GWP and CED levels during manufacture are due to high amounts of material used, particularly steel. Results are based on a high rate of recycling of steel and concrete being achieved. Significant differences in relative contributions of each life cycle stage across all 18 impact categories shows the importance of assessing more categories than the GWP and energy consumption for renewable technologies. Both energy and carbon payback times were found to be slightly below 2.5 years emphasizing once again the capability of renewable energy sources of paying back the energy and GHG emissions embedded in their life cycle.

The scenario analysis showed that there are alternative process and design choices that may improve the energy consumption and GHG emissions throughout the life cycle. While some scenarios showed a modest influence, others such as varying recycling rates and alternative material for stainless steel resulted in significant variations in the overall results. This is indicative of the importance of an in-depth analysis of the sensitivity of several parameters throughout the life cycle.

EoL is currently excluded from operational boundaries of the majority of MRE developments and its inclusion in eco-design initiatives is challenged by uncertainties on a temporal, technological and business level such as uncertainties regarding recycling ratios. This report corroborated with previous studies by proving the importance of the EoL scenario to the overall environmental performance and highlighted that a significant positive effect can be achieved if virgin materials can be replaced by recycled materials. Therefore, further efforts should be undertaken in order to better understand how to properly model this stage.

Some assumptions were made from earlier published studies and the re-use of secondary data may lead to errors propagating through the literature undetected.

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